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THE ROLE OF INVESTIGATION AGENCIES IN MAINTAINING NATIONAL PEACE AND ORDER IN PAKISTAN: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Investigation agencies in Pakistan play a crucial role in promoting justice and accountability by addressing a wide range of crimes and security threats. Despite facing challenges these agencies have achieved significant successes in investigating and prosecuting high-profile cases, disrupting terrorist networks, and protecting human rights. Their impact extends beyond law enforcement, contributing to strengthen democratic institutions, enhancing public trust in government, and fostering a culture of transparency and accountability. This paper delves into various ways in which investigation agencies in Pakistan contribute to the promotion of justice and accountability, addressing the challenges faced by investigation agencies of Pakistan. It finds that investment in technological advancements, coordination, transparency, and accountability is crucial for further enhancing the effectiveness of investigation agencies in Pakistan. By addressing these challenges and embracing best practices, Pakistan can advance its goals of justice, accountability, and the rule of law, thereby building a safer and more just society for all its citizens.

KEYWORDS: Accountability, Challenges, Investigation Agencies, Justice, Pakistan

1. INTRODUCTION

The promotion of justice and accountability through investigation agencies in Pakistan is a critical aspect of the country's governance and law enforcement framework. With a history marked by challenges related to corruption, terrorism, human rights violations, and organised crime, Pakistan relies heavily on its investigation agencies to uphold the rule of law, ensure transparency, and foster public trust in government institutions (Rasool, 2023).

This paper aims to explore the multifaceted role of investigation agencies in Pakistan in promoting justice and accountability, examining their functions, challenges, successes, and the broader impact on society.

1.1 Historical Context

Pakistan's journey towards establishing effective investigation agencies for promoting justice and accountability has been influenced by its historical, political, and socio-economic landscape. Since its independence in 1947, Pakistan has faced various governance challenges, including corruption, political instability, and security threats. These challenges have underscored the importance of robust law enforcement mechanisms and investigation agencies capable of addressing complex crime and security issues (Iqbal et al.,2023).

1.2 Evolution of Investigation Agencies

Over the years, Pakistan has developed a diverse array of investigation agencies at both federal and provincial levels to address different types of crimes and security threats. The establishment of agencies such as the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA), Intelligence Bureau (IB), National Accountability Bureau (NAB), and specialised units within provincial police forces reflects the country's efforts to adapt to evolving challenges and strengthen its law enforcement capabilities (Iqbal et al.,2023).

1.3 Functions and Responsibilities

Investigation agencies in Pakistan are tasked with a wide range of functions and responsibilities aimed at promoting justice and accountability. These include investigating crimes such as corruption, terrorism, and drug trafficking, human trafficking, cybercrime, and human rights violations. Additionally, investigation agencies play a crucial role in gathering evidence,

conducting surveillance, apprehending suspects, and presenting cases before courts for prosecution (Irshad, 2011).

1.4 Challenges and Constraints

Despite their importance, investigation agencies in Pakistan face numerous challenges and constraints that hinder their effectiveness in promoting justice and accountability. These challenges include resource constraints, political interference, institutional weaknesses, outdated legal frameworks, capacity gaps, and coordination issues. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive reforms, including investment in training, technology, infrastructure, and institutional capacity building (Rasool, 2023).

1.5 Successes and Achievements

Despite the challenges, investigation agencies in Pakistan have achieved notable successes in promoting justice and accountability. They have successfully investigated and prosecuted high-profile cases of corruption, terrorism, and other serious crimes, leading to convictions and the recovery of looted assets. Additionally, investigation agencies have played a crucial role in disrupting terrorist networks, dismantling criminal syndicates, and protecting human rights (Sadiq, 2020).

1.6 Impact on Society

The impact of investigation agencies on society extends beyond their direct law enforcement functions. By promoting justice and accountability, these agencies contribute to strengthening democratic institutions, enhancing public trust in government, deterring crime, protecting human rights, and fostering a culture of transparency and accountability. A society where justice is served and accountability is upheld is more resilient, stable, and prosperous (Sadiq, 2020).

1.7 Future Directions

The future of investigation agencies in Pakistan lies in addressing existing challenges, and embracing technological advancements, enhancing coordination and collaboration, improving transparency and accountability, and strengthening the rule of law. By investing in these areas, Pakistan can further enhance the effectiveness of its investigation agencies in promoting justice and accountability and building a safer and more just society for all its citizens (Rasool, 2023).

Hence, the promotion of justice and accountability through investigation agencies in Pakistan is essential for upholding the rule of law, ensuring transparency, and fostering public trust in

government institutions. Despite the challenges they face, investigation agencies play a crucial role in investigating crimes, prosecuting offenders, protecting human rights, and promoting a culture of accountability (Shah, 2007).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Investigation agencies play a pivotal role in safeguarding peace and order in Pakistan's dynamic socio-political landscape. Through their investigative prowess and enforcement actions, these agencies confront a myriad of challenges ranging from terrorism and organised crime to corruption and societal unrest. Understanding the multifaceted nature of their responsibilities and the evolving nature of threats is imperative to assess their effectiveness in maintaining stability. This literature review examines the role of investigation agencies in Pakistan, exploring their strategies, challenges, and contributions to peace and order in the country, thus providing valuable insights into the dynamics of law enforcement in the region.

Sarwar in his book entitled "Investigating Corruption in Pakistan: A Study of National Accountability Bureau" discusses several key problems e.g. resource Constraints, Political Interference, Coordination Issues, corruption and institutional weaknesses encountered by investigation agencies in Pakistan in their efforts to maintain peace and order. Sarwar finds that addressing these challenges is essential for improving the performance and effectiveness of investigation agencies in Pakistan and ensuring sustainable peace and order in the country (Sarwar,2016).

Mahmood et al in their research article entitled "The Role of the Judicial System and Law Enforcement Agencies in Combating Terrorism in Pakistan" examine the role of the FIA in ensuring national security and peace in Pakistan. Mahmood et al in their research paper analyse the functions, challenges, and successes of the FIA in combating crime, countering terrorism, and maintaining public order. Mahmood et al find that Lack of Resources, Technological Challenges, Coordination Issues, Legal Constraints and Political Interference are key problems faced by the FIA in its mission to ensure national security and peace. The aforementioned paper suggests the need for reforms, increased resources, improved coordination mechanisms, and strengthened legal frameworks to overcome these challenges and strengthen the FIA's role in maintaining security and peace in the country (Mahmood,2020).

Lieven in his book entitled “Pakistan: A Hard Country” Pakistan: A Hard Country “highlights several problems faced by investigation agencies in Pakistan, including corruption, political interference, resource constraints, and coordination issues. He discusses how these challenges undermine the effectiveness and credibility of investigation agencies, hindering their ability to maintain law and order and combat crime effectively. Lieven highlights several problems faced by investigation agencies in Pakistan, including corruption, political interference, resource constraints, and coordination issues. He discusses how these challenges undermine the effectiveness and credibility of investigation agencies, hindering their ability to maintain law and order and combat crime effectively. Lieven’s analysis reveals the significant challenges that investigation agencies encounter in Pakistan, emphasizing their systemic nature and deep-rooted origins. He underscores the complexities of Pakistan's governance and security landscape, which pose formidable obstacles to the functioning of investigation agencies. Lieven's findings underscore the need for comprehensive reforms and strategic interventions to address these challenges and strengthen the capacity and effectiveness of investigation agencies. Lieven offers suggestions for improving the role of investigation agencies in Pakistan, including enhancing transparency, accountability, and institutional capacity. He advocates for measures to reduce political interference, tackle corruption, and provide adequate resources and training to investigation agencies. Lieven also emphasizes the importance of fostering coordination and collaboration among different law enforcement bodies to enhance the overall effectiveness of investigation efforts. Overall, Lieven's recommendations emphasize the need for systemic reforms to enable investigation agencies to fulfill their mandate more effectively in Pakistan (Lieven, 2012).

Sadiq in his book entitled " Anti-corruption investigation agencies in Pakistan: an appraisal” highlights several problems faced by the NAB and other anti-corruption agencies in Pakistan, including political interference, lack of autonomy, resource constraints, legal loopholes, and challenges in evidence collection. He discusses how these issues hamper the effectiveness of corruption investigations and undermine public trust in anti-corruption efforts. Sarwar's analysis reveals the systemic weaknesses and institutional challenges within the NAB and the broader anti-corruption framework in Pakistan. He underscores the need for comprehensive reforms to address these issues and strengthen the capacity and integrity of anti-corruption agencies. Sadiq

offers suggestions for improving the effectiveness of corruption investigation in Pakistan, including enhancing the independence and autonomy of anti-corruption agencies, strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing transparency and accountability mechanisms, providing adequate resources and training, and fostering international cooperation in combating corruption. He emphasizes the importance of political will and public support in implementing these reforms to effectively tackle corruption and promote good governance in Pakistan (Sadiq, 2020).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research approach to investigate the role of investigation agencies in maintaining peace and order in Pakistan. Qualitative research allows for an in-depth exploration of complex phenomena, providing rich and nuanced insights into the subject matter. The secondary data sources used in the research include official reports, policy documents, and relevant literature pertaining to the role of investigation agencies in maintaining peace and order in Pakistan. These sources provide valuable background information, contextual insights, and historical perspectives on the subject matter. Additionally, secondary data sources help to complement and enrich the findings obtained from primary data collection methods such as interviews. By incorporating a diverse range of secondary data sources, the research aims to triangulate findings, validate interpretations, and ensure a comprehensive understanding of the challenges, strategies, and effectiveness of investigation agencies in promoting peace and order in Pakistan.

4. CRIME INVESTIGATION AND PREVENTION

Crime investigation and prevention through investigation agencies in Pakistan are essential components of maintaining peace and order in the country. Given the diverse range of criminal activities and security threats faced by Pakistan, investigation agencies play a crucial role in addressing these challenges effectively (Khan, 2016). Following paragraphs provide details of the role of the investigation agencies regarding crime investigation and crime prevention.

4.1 Efforts Regarding Crime Investigation

Maintaining law and order through investigation agencies in Pakistan is paramount for ensuring the safety, security, and well-being of its citizens. Investigation agencies, including the FIA, IB,

and provincial police forces, are instrumental in preventing crime, apprehending criminals, and upholding the rule of law (Mahmood & Ali, 2020).

Crime investigation in Pakistan involves thorough inquiries into various criminal activities such as homicide, robbery, cybercrime, and corruption. Investigation agencies employ forensic analysis, witness interviews, and digital forensics to gather evidence and identify perpetrators. Specialised units like the Anti-Narcotics Force (ANF) and Counter-Terrorism Department (CTD) target specific types of crime. Challenges such as resource constraints and political interference often hinder investigations, but these agencies play a vital role in maintaining law and order, ensuring justice, and upholding the rule of law in Pakistan (Iqbal & Mustafa, 2022).

Crime investigation in Pakistan involves thorough inquiries into various offenses using forensic analysis, witness interviews, and digital forensics. Specialised units within investigation agencies focus on homicide, robbery, cybercrime, and white-collar crime, contributing to law enforcement efforts and upholding the rule of law (Garcia, 2020).

Following paragraphs give details of the process.

4.1.1 Homicide Investigations: Investigation agencies in Pakistan conduct thorough inquiries into cases of homicide or murder. Homicide investigation units within police departments and specialised task forces in Pakistan, such as the Criminal Investigation Departments (CIDs) or Special Investigation Units (SIUs) and Anti-Terrorism Squad (ATS) operate under the provisions of the PPC, particularly Sections 302 to 304, which deal with the offense of murder or homicide. Additionally, these units adhere to the guidelines and procedures outlined in the Cr.P.C, including Sections 173 to 176, which specify the process for conducting investigations, gathering evidence, and presenting cases before the courts in homicide cases (Ahmed & Ali, 2019). These specialised task forces employ forensic analysis and detective work to gather evidence and apprehend perpetrators (Mateen & Tariq, 2019).

4.1.2 Robbery and Theft Investigations: Investigation agencies are tasked with investigating cases of robbery, theft, and burglary. Investigation agencies in Pakistan investigate cases of robbery, theft, and burglary under the PPC. Sections 392 to 402 address robbery, while theft is covered in Sections 378 to 382, and burglary in Sections 457 to 460. Agencies gather evidence, interview witnesses, and pursue suspects for prosecution. Through surveillance footage analysis, forensic examination of stolen property, and cooperation with the community, they track down

suspects and recover stolen goods. Specialised units within investigation agencies focus on addressing property crimes (Garcia, 2020). Coordination between law enforcement agencies and cooperation with the community are essential in solving these cases (Mateen & Tariq, 2019).

4.1.3 Cyber-crime Investigations: With the rise of technology, cyber-crime has become a significant challenge in Pakistan. Investigation agencies, such as the FIA Cyber-crime Wing, specialize in investigating offenses like hacking, online fraud, and identity theft. These agencies employ digital forensics, data analysis, and international cooperation to trace cybercriminals and disrupt their activities (Mahmood & Arif, 2020).

4.1.4 White-Collar Crime Investigations

White-collar crimes, encompassing fraud, corruption, embezzlement, and money laundering, pose substantial threats to Pakistan's economy and governance. Investigation agencies like the NAB are mandated to probe and prosecute individuals implicated in such offenses, including politicians, government officials, and business executives. These agencies frequently collaborate with financial institutions, regulatory bodies, and international organizations to uncover intricate financial crimes, which fall under the purview of various laws such as the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC) (1860), Anti-Money Laundering Act (2010), and other relevant statutes (Ali, 2022).

4.1.5 Counter-terrorism Operations: Counter-terrorism operations in Pakistan involve intelligence gathering, targeted raids, and legal action against terrorist groups. Specialised units like the CTD conduct operations to disrupt terrorist activities, apprehend suspects, and prevent attacks, contributing to national security and stability in the region. Details regarding counter terrorism operation are given in the following paragraphs

4.1.5.1 Intelligence Gathering: Investigation agencies in Pakistan collaborate closely with intelligence agencies such as the Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI), IB, and Military Intelligence (MI) to gather intelligence on terrorist organizations and their activities. This intelligence is used to identify and neutralize terrorist threats, prevent attacks, and dismantle terrorist networks operating within Pakistan.

4.1.5.2 Targeted Operations: Specialised units within investigation agencies, such as the CTD, conduct targeted operations against terrorist groups and individuals. These operations involve surveillance, raids, and arrests aimed at disrupting terrorist activities and apprehending suspects.

4.1.5.3 Prosecution and Legal Action: Investigation agencies collect evidence to build strong cases against terrorists, ensuring fair and transparent trials in accordance with Pakistani laws. Convictions are sought based on the strength of evidence presented in court, leading to the imprisonment or sentencing of terrorists.

4.2 Efforts regarding crime prevention

Investigation agencies in Pakistan play a crucial role in crime prevention by employing various strategies aimed at deterring criminal activities, investigating offenses, and dismantling criminal networks. These agencies, including the FIA, IB, CID, Anti-Corruption Establishment (ACE) and provincial police forces, are tasked with maintaining law and order, protecting citizens, and ensuring public safety under various laws such as the PPC (1860), Anti-Terrorism Act (ATA) (1997), and relevant provincial laws and regulations. Through proactive measures such as intelligence gathering, targeted operations, and community engagement, investigation agencies strive to prevent crimes before they occur (Ali, 2022). By analyzing crime trends, identifying emerging threats, and collaborating with other law enforcement agencies, they work to disrupt criminal activities and apprehend offenders swiftly (Asghar et al., 2023).

Following paragraphs provide details of the working of investigation agencies.

4.2.1 Community Policing Initiatives

Investigation agencies in Pakistan, such as the FIA, IB, and provincial police forces, engage in community policing initiatives. They collaborate with local law enforcement agencies, community leaders, and residents to implement programs aimed at building trust, fostering cooperation, and empowering communities to play an active role in crime prevention. These initiatives often include community outreach events, neighborhood watch programs, youth engagement activities, and educational campaigns to raise awareness about crime prevention strategies and promote safety within communities (Asghar et al., 2023).

4.2.2 Intelligence-Led Policing

Intelligence-led policing is a proactive approach to crime prevention that relies on gathering and analysing intelligence to identify and mitigate potential threats. Investigation agencies in Pakistan collaborate with intelligence agencies, such as the Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) and IB, to gather information on criminal organizations, terrorist networks, and other security threats. This intelligence is used to develop strategies for targeting high-risk areas, disrupting criminal

activities, and apprehending suspects before they can commit crimes under various laws such as the PPC (1860), ATA (1997), and relevant intelligence and security legislation (Abbas, 2011).

4.2.3 Specialised Task Forces

Several investigation agencies such as counter-terrorism task forces, anti-corruption task forces, cyber-crime investigation units, narcotics control units, human trafficking units, financial crimes investigation units, organised crime units, and white-collar crime task forces in Pakistan are dedicated to address specific types of crime or security threats. For example, the ANF focuses on combating drug trafficking and drug abuse, while the CTD targets terrorist networks and extremist organizations. These task forces employ specialised training, equipment, and tactics to tackle complex challenges effectively (Butt, 2022).

4.2.4 Public Awareness Campaigns

In Pakistan, crime prevention efforts often entail public awareness campaigns aimed at educating citizens about prevalent crimes and safety measures. Investigation agencies such as the FIA, IB, and provincial police forces collaborate with media outlets, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and community leaders to disseminate information and raise awareness about crime prevention strategies. These initiatives empower Pakistani citizens to protect themselves and their communities from criminal activities, contributing to the establishment of a safer and more secure society (UNODC, 2017).

4.2.5 Emergency Response: Investigation agencies, including the FIA, IB, and provincial police forces, collaborate with specialised units like the Rescue 1122 service to respond swiftly to emergencies such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and public health crises. These agencies coordinate efforts to provide emergency medical assistance, firefighting, and disaster response services to ensure public safety during critical situations.

4.3 Counter-terrorism Operations

Counter-terrorism operations through investigation authorities in Pakistan are integral to combating the persistent threat posed by terrorism in the country. Given Pakistan's geopolitical landscape and history of militant activities, investigation agencies in Pakistan, through intelligence gathering, surveillance, and targeted investigations, work to identify and dismantle terrorist networks, disrupt their activities, and apprehend perpetrators. Their efforts contribute significantly to safeguarding national security, protecting citizens from terrorist attacks, and

maintaining stability in the region (Aslam, 2015). Following paragraphs give detail of the working

4.3.1 Intelligence Gathering and Analysis

Investigation authorities, such as the FIA and IB, collaborate closely with intelligence agencies like the ISI to gather intelligence on terrorist organizations, their activities, and their networks. These agencies employ various means, including human intelligence, signals intelligence, and open-source intelligence, to collect actionable intelligence for counter-terrorism operations.

Based on intelligence inputs and threat assessments, investigation agencies analyse the capabilities, intentions, and potential targets of terrorist groups. This analysis helps these investigation agencies prioritize resources, deploy personnel, and plan operations to mitigate threats effectively (Rana, 2019).

4.3.2 Targeted Operations and Raids

Targeted operations and raids by investigation agencies in Pakistan are critical components of counter-terrorism efforts. These operations involve intelligence-driven strategies to identify and neutralize terrorist threats swiftly and effectively. Specialised units within investigation agencies conduct raids based on actionable intelligence, targeting terrorist hideouts, training camps, and high-value targets. These operations often require meticulous planning, coordination, and execution to minimize collateral damage and ensure the safety of law enforcement personnel and civilians. Through targeted operations and raids, investigation agencies play a crucial role in disrupting terrorist networks, dismantling their infrastructure, and enhancing national security (Rana, 2019).

4.3.3 Collaboration with Law Enforcement Agencies

Investigation agencies collaborate with law enforcement agencies, such as the police and paramilitary forces, to form joint task forces and specialised units dedicated to counter-terrorism operations under the ATA, 1997 of Pakistan. These units, such as the CTD and ATS, receive specialised training and equipment to combat terrorism effectively.

Seamless coordination and information sharing between investigation authorities and law enforcement agencies are essential for successful counter-terrorism operations. Regular intelligence briefings, joint operations, and task force meetings facilitate collaboration and enhance operational effectiveness (Rasool, 2018).

4.3.4 Prosecution and Legal Action

In Pakistan, investigation authorities collect evidence and conduct counter-terrorism operations in accordance with various laws and regulations, including the ATA of 1997, the Code of Criminal Procedure (Cr.P.C) of 1898, the PPC, and the Pakistan Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) of 2016. These laws outline procedures for obtaining search warrants, conducting arrests, gathering evidence, and prosecuting suspects. They ensure that counter-terrorism operations are carried out within the legal framework, respecting the rights of individuals and upholding the principles of justice and due process (Hussain& Khan,2017).

4.3.5 De-radicalisation and Rehabilitation

Investigation authorities collaborate with government agencies, civil society organizations, and religious leaders to implement de-radicalization and rehabilitation programs for individuals involved in terrorism. These programs aim to address the root causes of radicalization, provide psychological counseling, vocational training, and educational opportunities to facilitate the reintegration of former militants into society (Hussain & Khan, 2017).

4.4 Challenges Faced By Investigation Agencies

The investigation agencies in Pakistan encounter multifaceted challenges in their pursuit of maintaining law and order. From combating terrorism to addressing organised crime and corruption, these agencies face significant hurdles that impede their effectiveness. Understanding and addressing these challenges are crucial for enhancing the capabilities of investigation agencies and ensuring the safety and security of the nation. This paper explores the various challenges faced by investigation agencies in Pakistan and discusses potential strategies to overcome them, thereby contributing to the advancement of law enforcement and justice in the country (Rasool, 2018).

The complex and evolving landscape of terrorist threats, encompassing both domestic and international terrorist organizations, presents formidable obstacles for investigation authorities in Pakistan. These threats vary in their scope, tactics, and targets, requiring a multifaceted approach to counter them effectively. From extremist ideologies to sophisticated networks, the diversity of these threats demands constant vigilance and adaptive strategies from law enforcement agencies. Investigation authorities must navigate through this intricate terrain, leveraging intelligence,

technology, and collaboration to stay ahead of emerging threats and safeguards national security and public safety (Akhtar & Shah, 2017).

Limited funding, outdated equipment, and insufficient training impede the effectiveness of counter-terrorism operations conducted by investigation authorities. Political pressure, interference, and influence often undermine the autonomy and impartiality of investigation authorities, hindering their ability to conduct objective and effective counter-terrorism operations (Abbas & Rehman, 2018).

In Pakistan, investigation authorities grapple with the delicate balance between national security and safeguarding human rights and civil liberties, especially concerning the handling and legal proceedings involving terror suspects. These challenges are rooted in several human rights frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and Pakistan's Constitution. Pertinent sections of these laws include Article 9 (Right to Liberty and Security of Person), Article 14 (Right to Fair Trial), Article 19 (Freedom of Speech), and Article 25 (Equality of Citizens). Ensuring compliance with these rights while combating terrorism requires careful adherence to the legal and procedural safeguards outlined in pertinent sections of these laws (Abbas & Rehman, 2018).

In short, counter-terrorism operations through investigation authorities in Pakistan are vital for combating the persistent threat of terrorism in the country. Through intelligence gathering, targeted operations, collaboration with law enforcement agencies, prosecution, and rehabilitation efforts, these authorities play a crucial role in identifying, disrupting, and neutralizing terrorist networks. Despite facing challenges such as resource constraints, political interference, and human rights concerns, investigation authorities remain committed to safeguarding national security and promoting peace and stability in Pakistan (Saleem & Javed, 2020). Details of the challenges faced by investigation agencies in Pakistan are as follows.

4.4.1 Resource Constraints: One of the primary challenges faced by investigation agencies in Pakistan is resource constraints. Limited funding and inadequate technological resources hinder their ability to conduct thorough investigations and gather sufficient evidence. Insufficient manpower also affects their capacity to respond effectively to criminal incidents and carry out proactive crime prevention initiatives (Sarwar, 2016).

4.4.2 Legal Complexities: In Pakistan, the legal framework governing crime investigation and prevention faces several challenges due to its complexity and outdated nature. Ambiguities or conflicts within the PPC or the Cr.P.C can arise from various sections or articles. For instance, discrepancies in interpreting Section 34 of the PPC, which deals with acts done by several persons in furtherance of common intention, may impede effective crime investigation. Similarly, questions may arise regarding the boundaries of self-defense and justifiable use of force under Section 100 of the PPC. In the Cr.P.C, challenges may emerge in determining the extension of remand periods and the rights of detainees during extended custody under Section 167. Ambiguities or conflicts within laws can create confusion and hinder law enforcement efforts. Outdated laws, such as sections of the PPC or the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act 2016 (PECA), may fail to address emerging forms of crime adequately, particularly in the digital realm. These laws may lack specific provisions or definitions to effectively combat new criminal tactics in cyberspace, reflecting their outdated nature. For example, provisions related to cyber-crime in the PPC or PECA may not encompass modern cyber threats such as hacking, online fraud, or identity theft, thereby hindering law enforcement agencies' ability to address such offenses effectively. As a result, these laws may require updates or amendments to align with contemporary challenges in cyber-crime prevention and prosecution.

Additionally, the judicial processes in Pakistan are often lengthy and cumbersome, leading to delays in the prosecution of offenders and the delivery of justice. Overburdened courts, procedural inefficiencies, and the backlog of cases further exacerbate these delays, making it difficult for investigation agencies to bring criminals to justice in a timely manner. Moreover, loopholes in existing legislation can be exploited by perpetrators to evade accountability. For instance, legal loopholes may allow for lenient sentencing or provide avenues for corruption and influence peddling, undermining the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts (Masudi & Mustafa, 2023).

4.4.3 Operational Hurdles: Operational challenges, such as coordination issues and jurisdictional conflicts, further complicate the work of investigation agencies in Pakistan. Lack of inter-agency cooperation and information sharing impedes collaboration between different law enforcement entities, hindering the exchange of critical intelligence and hindering joint operations against criminal networks. Additionally, overlapping jurisdictional boundaries among

federal, provincial, and local agencies can lead to gaps in coverage and duplication of efforts (Masudi & Mustafa, 2023).

4.4.4 Corruption and Political Interference: Corruption and political interference present significant challenges to crime investigation and prevention in Pakistan. Influence peddling, bribery, and political patronage often undermine the integrity of law enforcement agencies and compromise the impartiality of investigations. Political interference in the appointment of senior officials and the allocation of resources may also undermine the autonomy and effectiveness of investigation agencies (Sarwar, 2016).

4.4.5 Socio-Cultural Factors: Socio-cultural factors, including widespread poverty, illiteracy, and social inequality, contribute to the prevalence of crime in Pakistan and pose challenges to crime investigation and prevention efforts. Socio-economic disparities exacerbate vulnerabilities to criminal exploitation, while cultural norms and traditions may discourage victims from reporting crimes or cooperating with law enforcement agencies (khan et al, 2015).

In essence, investigation agencies in Pakistan are integral to investigate and prevent various forms of criminal activities, spanning from violent crimes like homicide and robbery to sophisticated offenses like cyber-crime and white-collar crime. Their roles encompass gathering evidence, conducting thorough investigations, and implementing strategies to prevent crime, all aimed at upholding peace and order in Pakistan. Nonetheless, these agencies encounter notable obstacles such as limited resources, corruption, coordination issues, and technological deficiencies, which must be overcome to bolster their effectiveness in combating crime and ensuring the safety and security of all citizens (M Umer Rafique, 2023).

4.5 Specialised Units and Task Forces

Investigation agencies in Pakistan have established specialised units and task forces to effectively address specific types of crimes and security threats. These specialised units employ advanced techniques, specialised training, and dedicated resources to tackle complex challenges which are as follows

4.5.1 Federal Investigation Agency (FIA): The FIA is a premier investigation agency in Pakistan responsible for addressing a wide range of criminal activities, including cybercrime, human trafficking, immigration offenses, and financial fraud. The FIA of Pakistan was formed under the Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974. This law provides the legal framework for the

establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the FIA in investigating and prosecuting federal crimes, including cybercrime, human trafficking, immigration offenses, and terrorism-related activities. Established in 1975, the FIA operates under the Ministry of Interior and serves as the primary federal law enforcement agency in the country (The FIA Act, 1974).

With its headquarters in Islamabad, the FIA operates across Pakistan through its regional offices and specialised wings. One of its key functions is to investigate crimes that have a transnational or interstate dimension, making it crucial for maintaining national security and integrity. Its important wings are as follows:-

4.5.1.1 Cyber-crime Wing: The FIA Cyber-crime Wing in Pakistan was established under the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA), 2016. This legislation provides the legal framework for addressing cybercrimes, including offenses related to unauthorized access to information systems, electronic fraud, cyber-terrorism, and online harassment. The FIA cyber-crime Wing operates under the authority of PECA to investigate and prosecute cyber-related offenses in Pakistan.

The FIA Cyber-crime Wing specializes in investigating cybercrimes such as hacking, online fraud, and identity theft. Equipped with digital forensics tools and expertise, this unit combats cyber threats and ensures the safety of digital transactions and information (The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act, 2016).

4.5.1.2 Anti-Human Trafficking Cell: The FIA's Anti-Human Trafficking Cell in Pakistan was established under the Prevention of Trafficking in Persons Act, 2018. This legislation provides the legal framework for addressing human trafficking offenses and protecting victims of trafficking. The Anti-Human Trafficking Cell operates under the authority of this law to investigate and prosecute cases related to human trafficking in Pakistan. The Anti-Human Trafficking Cell focuses on combating human trafficking and smuggling networks operating within Pakistan. Tasked with rescuing victims and apprehending traffickers, this unit collaborates with international agencies to dismantle transnational trafficking rings (The Prevention of Trafficking in Persons Act, 2018).

4.5.1.3 Counter-terrorism Wing

The FIA Counter-Terrorism Wing was established under the Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974. While the Act primarily focuses on investigative and enforcement powers related to

various federal crimes, it also empowers the FIA to establish specialised units or wings, including the Counter-Terrorism Wing, to address specific threats and challenges related to terrorism within Pakistan (The FIA Act, 1974).The hierarchy of the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) of Pakistan typically includes the following positions:-

Table 1.1 Hierarchy of the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) of Pakistan

S.No.	Designation	Responsibilities
1	Director General (DG)	The head of the FIA, responsible for overall leadership, management, and direction.
2	Additional Director Generals (Addl. DGs)	Assist the DG in overseeing specific functions or departments within the FIA and may act as deputies in their absence.
3	Directors	Head various departments or divisions within the FIA, responsible for managing specific areas of investigation, enforcement, and operations.
4	Additional Directors (Addl. Directors)	Assist directors in managing specific tasks or functions within their respective departments.
5	Deputy Directors (DDs)	Assist in overseeing operational activities, investigations, and enforcement efforts within specific units or divisions.
6	Assistant Directors (ADs)	Supervise field operations, investigations, and administrative tasks within designated areas or units.
7	Inspectors	Conduct investigations, gather evidence, and supervise lower-ranking personnel in carrying out operational tasks.
8	Sub-Inspectors	Assist inspectors in conducting investigations and gathering evidence.
9	Assistant Sub-Inspectors (ASI)	Provide support to inspectors and sub-inspectors in their duties.
10	Investigation Officers	Conduct investigative tasks under the supervision of senior officials, including gathering evidence, interviewing witnesses, and preparing case reports.
11	Support Staff	Provide administrative, logistical, and technical support to FIA operations, including clerical staff, IT specialists, and maintenance personnel.

This hierarchy may vary based on the specific organizational structure, size, and operational requirements of the FIA. Additionally, the FIA may have specialised units or task forces with their own hierarchical structures.

4.5.2 Intelligence Bureau (IB)

The IB of Pakistan is the country's premier civilian intelligence agency, tasked with gathering, analyzing, and disseminating intelligence related to national security and internal stability. Established in 1947, shortly after the creation of Pakistan, the IB operates under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Interior and is headquartered in Islamabad.

The IB plays a pivotal role in safeguarding Pakistan's sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national interests. Its primary responsibilities include counterintelligence, counter-terrorism, and the monitoring of subversive activities aimed at destabilizing the country.

Operating both domestically and internationally, the IB maintains a network of intelligence operatives and assets to collect information on potential threats, including espionage, terrorism, and organised crime. Through its surveillance capabilities, analysis of open-source intelligence and cooperation with other intelligence agencies, the IB provides actionable intelligence to decision-makers and law enforcement agencies (Grare, 2009).

The IB's Counter-terrorism Wing is particularly significant in Pakistan's efforts to combat extremism and terrorism. By identifying terrorist networks, tracking their activities, and disrupting their operations, the IB contributes to maintaining security and stability within the country.

Throughout its history, the IB has adapted to evolving security challenges, demonstrating professionalism, dedication, and effectiveness in fulfilling its mandate as Pakistan's primary civilian intelligence agency (Gosling, 2016). Its two wings are as follows

4.5.2.1 Counter-intelligence Wing: The IB Counterintelligence Wing is responsible for identifying and neutralizing espionage activities, foreign intelligence operations, and subversive threats to national security. Through surveillance, analysis, and countermeasures, this unit safeguards Pakistan's sovereignty and interests.

4.5.2.2 Counter-terrorism Wing: The IB Counter-terrorism Wing gathers intelligence on terrorist organizations, their activities, and networks. Tasked with preventing terrorist attacks and disrupting terrorist financing, this unit plays a vital role in countering extremism and promoting stability. The hierarchy of the IB of Pakistan typically includes the following positions:

Table 1.2: The Hierarchy of the Intelligence Bureau (IB) of Pakistan.

S.No.	Designation	Responsibilities
1	Director General (DG)	The head of the Intelligence Bureau, responsible for overall leadership, management, and direction.
2	Additional Director Generals (Addl. DGs)	Assist the DG in overseeing specific functions or departments within the IB and may act as deputies in their absence.
3	Directors	Head various departments or divisions within the IB, responsible for managing specific areas of intelligence gathering, analysis, and operations.
4	Additional Directors (Addl. Directors)	Assist directors in managing specific tasks or functions within their respective departments.
5	Deputy Directors (DDs)	Assist in overseeing operational activities, investigations, and intelligence

		collection efforts within specific units or divisions.
6	Assistant Directors (ADs)	Supervise field operations, intelligence gathering activities, and administrative tasks within designated areas or units.
7	Section Officers	Manage specific sections or units within departments, responsible for coordination, reporting, and administrative tasks.
8	Intelligence Officers	Conduct intelligence gathering, analysis, and reporting activities under the supervision of senior officials.
9	Support Staff	Provide administrative, logistical, and technical support to IB operations, including clerical staff, IT specialists, and maintenance personnel.

However, the hierarchy within the IB may differ according to its unique organizational framework, size, and operational needs. Moreover, specialised units or task forces within the IB may possess distinct hierarchical arrangements tailored to their specific functions.

4.5.3 National Accountability Bureau (NAB)

The NAB of Pakistan is the apex anti-corruption organization responsible for investigating and prosecuting cases of corruption, financial mismanagement, and maladministration at the national level. Established in 1999 under the National Accountability Ordinance (NAO) 1999, the NAB operates independently to ensure accountability, transparency, and integrity in governance and public administration (The NAO, 1999).

Headquartered in Islamabad, the NAB has regional offices across Pakistan to facilitate its investigative and enforcement activities. Its mandate includes combating corruption in government institutions, recovering ill-gotten assets, and holding public officials accountable for their actions.

The NAB’s Anti-Corruption Wing conducts thorough investigations into cases of corruption, bribery, embezzlement, and abuse of power. By enforcing strict accountability measures and prosecuting offenders, the NAB plays a crucial role in promoting good governance, combating financial crimes, and safeguarding public resources. Details of its important wings are as follows:-

4.5.3.1 Anti-Corruption Wing: The NAB Anti-Corruption Wing was established under the NAO, 1999. This ordinance provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the NAB, including its Anti-Corruption Wing. The Anti-Corruption Wing is

tasked with investigating and prosecuting cases of corruption, financial mismanagement, and other related offenses in Pakistan. The NAB Anti-Corruption Wing investigates corruption, fraud, and embezzlement cases involving government officials, politicians, and public servants. With a focus on accountability and transparency, this unit aims to combat corruption and promote good governance (The NAO, 1999).

4.5.3.2 Financial Monitoring Unit: The Financial Monitoring Unit (FMU) of the NAB in Pakistan was established under the NAO, 1999. This ordinance provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the NAB, including its specialised units like the FMU. The FMU is responsible for monitoring financial transactions, detecting money laundering, and investigating financial crimes in accordance with the provisions of the NAO and relevant anti-money laundering laws and regulations. The Financial Monitoring Unit tracks suspicious financial transactions, money laundering activities, and illicit funds flowing through Pakistan's financial system (The NAO, 1999). By analyzing financial data and enforcing anti-money laundering laws, this unit disrupts illicit financial networks.

The hierarchy of the NAB of Pakistan typically includes the following positions:

1.3 Table: The Hierarchy of the National Accountability Bureau (NAB) of Pakistan.

S.No.	Designation	Responsibilities
1	Chairman	The head of NAB, responsible for overall leadership, direction, and management of the organization.
2	Prosecutor General Accountability (PGA)	Chief legal officer responsible for overseeing prosecution matters and representing NAB in court proceedings.
3	Director General (DG)	Heads regional or departmental offices of NAB and oversees the implementation of NAB's policies and strategies.
4	Additional Director General (Addl. DG)	Assists the DG in managing specific functions or regions within NAB.
5	Deputy Director General (DDG)	Assists in managing specific departments or functions within NAB.
6	Directors	Heads investigation teams and supervises operational activities within NAB.
7	Additional Director (Addl. Director)	Assists directors in managing specific cases or operations.
8	Deputy Director (DD)	Leads investigative teams and manages case files.
9	Assistant Director (AD)	Conducts investigations, gathers evidence, and prepares case reports under the supervision of senior officials.

10	Investigation Officer (IO)	Executes investigative tasks under the supervision of directors or deputy directors.
11	Prosecutor	Represents NAB in court proceedings and presents prosecution evidence.
12	Assistant Prosecutor	Assists prosecutors in legal matters and court proceedings.
13	Support Staff	Provides administrative, logistical, and technical support to NAB operations, including clerical staff, IT specialists, and maintenance personnel.

However, the hierarchy could differ depending on the particular organizational layout, scale, and operational necessities of the NAB. Furthermore, specialised units or task forces within the NAB might possess distinct hierarchical arrangements of their own.

4.6 Provincial Police Forces

At provincial level following counter terrorism departments are working

4.6.1 Counter-terrorism Departments (CTDs) Provincial CTDs are specialised units within police forces dedicated to countering terrorism and extremism. These departments conduct intelligence-based operations, raids, and arrests to disrupt terrorist activities and protect civilians from security threats. The Punjab Provincial CTD in Pakistan was established under the Punjab Counter-terrorism Department Act, 2013. This legislation provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the Punjab CTD in Punjab province. The Punjab CTD is responsible for conducting counter-terrorism operations, investigating terrorist activities, and maintaining law and order in the Punjab province.

The Sindh Provincial CTD in Pakistan was established under the Sindh Arms Act, 2013. This legislation provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the Sindh CTD in Sindh province. The Sindh CTD is responsible for conducting counter-terrorism operations, investigating terrorist activities, and maintaining law and order in the Sindh province.

The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) Provincial CTD in Pakistan was established under the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Arms Ordinance, 2013. This ordinance provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the KPK CTD in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. The KPK CTD is responsible for conducting counter-terrorism operations, investigating terrorist activities, and maintaining law and order in the KPK province.

The Baluchistan Provincial CTD in Pakistan was established under the Baluchistan Arms Ordinance, 2015. This ordinance provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of the Baluchistan CTD in Baluchistan province. The Baluchistan CTD is responsible for conducting counter-terrorism operations, investigating terrorist activities, and maintaining law and order in the Baluchistan.

4.6.1.1 Special Investigation Units (SIUs)

SIUs in Pakistan are typically established under the jurisdiction of provincial police departments. The SIUs in Punjab, Pakistan, are established under the Punjab Police Order, 2002. This law provides the legal framework for the establishment, functions, and jurisdiction of various units within the Punjab Police, including SIUs. The Punjab Police Order, 2002, outlines the powers, duties, and responsibilities of the police force in the province and governs the establishment and operation of specialised units such as SIUs to investigate high-profile cases such as assassinations, organised crime including drug trafficking and human smuggling, and serious offenses like homicide and financial fraud. The SIUs in Sindh, Pakistan, are typically established under the Sindh Police Act, 1861, and subsequent amendments and ordinances. The Sindh Police Act provides the legal framework for the organization, functions, and jurisdiction of the police force in the province, including the establishment of specialised units like SIUs. Additionally, administrative orders and directives issued by the Sindh government or the Inspector General of Police may further regulate the establishment and operation of SIUs within the province. The SIUs in KPK, Pakistan, are established under the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Act, 2017. This law provides the legal framework for the organization, functions, and jurisdiction of the police force in the province, including the establishment of specialised units like SIUs. The Special Investigation Units (SIUs) in Baluchistan, Pakistan, are established under the Baluchistan Police Act, 2011. This legislation provides the legal framework for the organization, functions, and jurisdiction of the police force in the province, including the establishment of specialised units like SIUs. The Baluchistan Police Act, 2011, outlines the powers, duties, and responsibilities of the police force and governs the establishment and operation of SIUs to investigate high-profile cases such as assassinations, organised crime including drug trafficking and human smuggling, and serious offenses like homicide and financial fraud within the Baluchistan province.

SIUs within provincial police forces focus on investigating high-profile cases such as assassinations, organised crime including drug trafficking and human smuggling, and serious offenses like homicide and financial fraud. Equipped with specialised training and resources, these units handle complex investigations and ensure the prosecution of offenders.

4.7 Specialised Task Forces

Specialised task forces in Pakistan are dedicated units established to address specific challenges, ranging from counter-terrorism to narcotics trafficking. These task forces operate within various law enforcement agencies and paramilitary organizations, employing specialised skills, resources, and strategies to combat complex threats effectively. Following special task forces are working in Pakistan.

4.7.1 Anti-Narcotics Force (ANF) The ANF in Pakistan was established under the Anti-Narcotics Force Act, 1997. This law provides the legal framework for the organization, functions, and jurisdiction of the ANF in combating narcotics trafficking and related offenses in Pakistan. Through interdiction operations, intelligence gathering, and international cooperation, this force targets drug cartels and dismantles drug smuggling networks (The ANF Act, 1997).

4.7.2 Counter-terrorism Wing (CTW)

The CTW in Pakistan was established in 2003 under the ATA of 1997. This law provides the legal framework for the organization, functions, and jurisdiction of the CTW in addressing terrorism-related threats and activities within the country. The CTW operates as a specialised unit within law enforcement agencies, focusing on intelligence gathering, surveillance, and targeted operations to counter terrorist organizations and prevent acts of terrorism. It collaborates closely with other national and international security agencies to enhance Pakistan's capabilities in combating terrorism and maintaining peace and security (Firdous, 2017).

Hence, specialised units and task forces within investigation agencies in Pakistan play a crucial role in addressing specific types of crimes and security threats. From cyber-crime to terrorism, corruption to narcotics trafficking, these units employ specialised skills, resources, and strategies to combat complex challenges effectively. By enhancing coordination, collaboration, and capacity-building efforts, Pakistan can further strengthen the capabilities of these specialised units and ensure the safety and security of its citizens (Abbas, 2011).

4.8 International Co-operations

Law enforcement agencies worldwide, including those in Pakistan, grapple with significant challenges posed by transnational criminal activities such as drug trafficking, human trafficking, terrorism, and cybercrime. These crimes often transcend national borders, requiring coordinated efforts among countries to combat them effectively. Collaborative initiatives between investigation agencies in Pakistan and their counterparts in other countries and international organizations are essential to address these challenges and mitigate the threats posed by transnational criminal networks (Clapper, 2013).

4.8.1 Importance of Transnational Cooperation

Criminal activities such as terrorism, drug trafficking, human trafficking, and cyber-crime transcend national borders, requiring collaborative efforts to investigate and combat them effectively. Transnational cooperation enables investigation agencies to gather intelligence, share information, and coordinate operations across jurisdictions. Collaboration with international partners allows investigation agencies in Pakistan to access specialised expertise, resources, and technologies not available domestically (Haider, 2023). This enhances their capabilities in conducting complex investigations, gathering evidence, and prosecuting offenders involved in transnational crimes. The collaborative efforts of investigation agencies in Pakistan with international partners to combat transnational crimes are conducted under various international agreements, conventions, and protocols. These may include bilateral agreements between countries, as well as multilateral agreements facilitated by organizations such as the United Nations and INTERPOL. Additionally, specific laws and regulations within Pakistan, such as the Mutual Legal Assistance Ordinance 2000, may govern aspects of international cooperation in criminal matters (Haider, 2023).

4.8.2 Mechanisms of Transnational Cooperation

Pakistan employs diverse mechanisms for transnational cooperation, including bilateral agreements, mutual legal assistance treaties, and memoranda of understanding. These agreements facilitate collaboration with neighboring nations and international organizations, enabling information exchange and joint operations to combat transnational crimes effectively, such as terrorism, drug trafficking, and cybercrime. Details are given in the following paragraphs:-

1. Pakistan has strategically pursued bilateral agreements and international conventions to strengthen its collaboration in law enforcement and combat transnational crime. Bilateral agreements include the Extradition Treaty signed with the United States in 1931, facilitating the extradition of individuals suspected of committing crimes in either country. Additionally, mutual legal assistance agreements with countries like Turkey, signed in 1995, enable Pakistan to request and provide assistance in criminal investigations and proceedings.
2. Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with neighboring nations such as Iran and Afghanistan further enhance cooperation in counter-terrorism efforts. For instance, the MoU signed with Iran in 2013 aims to improve border security and intelligence sharing to combat terrorism and drug trafficking.
3. Furthermore, Pakistan's commitment to international conventions like the UN Convention against Transnational Organised Crime (2000) and the UN Convention against Corruption (2003) underscores its dedication to combat transnational crime through multilateral cooperation and coordination with other member states. These agreements and conventions provide essential frameworks for information exchange, joint operations, and legal cooperation, bolstering Pakistan's efforts to address transnational criminal activities effectively.
4. Investigation agencies in Pakistan collaborate with international partners to counter terrorist threats and dismantle terrorist networks operating across borders. Information sharing, joint investigations, and coordinated operations are essential for disrupting terrorist activities and preventing attacks (Abbas, 2011).

Transnational drug trafficking networks pose significant challenges to law enforcement agencies in Pakistan. Collaboration with international partners, particularly neighboring countries and drug-producing regions, is crucial for intercepting drug shipments, dismantling trafficking networks, and reducing drug-related crimes (Haider, 2023).

With the increasing prevalence of cybercrime, collaboration with international partners is essential for investigating cyber attacks, identifying cybercriminals, and combating online fraud and identity theft. Information sharing, capacity-building initiatives and joint task forces enhance the ability of investigation agencies to address cyber threats effectively (Abbas, 2011).

Differences in legal systems, jurisdictional boundaries, and extradition laws among countries can complicate transnational cooperation efforts. Harmonizing legal frameworks, streamlining

extradition procedures, and addressing jurisdictional challenges are essential for effective collaboration.

Political tensions, diplomatic disputes, and geopolitical rivalries may hinder cooperation between countries, particularly in sensitive areas such as counter-terrorism and intelligence sharing. Building trust, fostering dialogue, and depoliticizing law enforcement efforts are necessary to overcome political obstacles (Haider, 2023).

4.8.3 Benefits of Transnational Co-operation

Transnational cooperation enables investigation agencies to access and share intelligence, expertise, and best practices with their counterparts worldwide. This facilitates timely and comprehensive responses to emerging threats and enhances situational awareness.

Collaborative efforts among investigation agencies increase the effectiveness of operations targeting transnational criminals and terrorist organizations. Coordinated investigations, joint operations, and intelligence fusion enable law enforcement agencies to disrupt criminal activities and apprehend offenders more efficiently (Andreas, 2008).

Therefore, transnational cooperation among investigation agencies in Pakistan is essential for combating the increasingly complex and interconnected nature of crime and security threats. By engaging in collaborative efforts with their counterparts in other countries and international organizations, investigation agencies can enhance their capabilities, expand their reach, and effectively address transnational challenges. Overcoming challenges, fostering partnerships, and promoting information sharing are critical for ensuring the success of transnational cooperation efforts and safeguarding the safety, security, and well-being of people in Pakistan and beyond (Andreas and Nadelmann 2008).

4.9 Promotions of Justice and Accountability

Justice and accountability are foundational principles for the rule of law and the functioning of a democratic society. In Pakistan, issues of corruption, human rights violations, and impunity have historically challenged the justice system (Iqbal, 2015). Investigation agencies of Pakistan play a crucial role in promoting justice and ensuring accountability in following ways:-

4.9.1 Combating Corruption

The NAB is Pakistan's apex anti-corruption agency, tasked with investigating and prosecuting cases of corruption, embezzlement, and abuse of power. By conducting impartial and thorough

investigations, the NAB holds public officials and individuals accountable for misusing public resources and violating the public trust (Imran et al, 2023).

The FIA's Anti-Corruption Wing investigates corruption cases at the federal level, focusing on offenses such as bribery, fraud, and money laundering. Through its efforts, the FIA contributes to promoting accountability and integrity within government institutions (Sheikh & Khan, 2023).

4.9.2 Ensuring Fair Trials

Investigation agencies in Pakistan, such as the FIA, IB, and provincial police forces, collaborate with prosecutors to prepare cases and present evidence in court. These agencies gather evidence through various means, including forensic analysis, witness interviews, and digital forensics, to build strong cases against individuals accused of committing crimes. By adhering to due process and ensuring fair trials, investigation agencies contribute to uphold the principles of justice and hold perpetrators accountable for their actions. Furthermore, specialised teams of the FIA's Cyber-crime Wing gather digital evidence and investigate cybercrimes to strengthen prosecution efforts in Pakistan (Shaikh and Khan, 2023).

4.9.3 Protecting Human Rights

Investigation agencies have a responsibility to uphold human rights standards while conducting investigations and apprehending suspects. This includes respecting the rights of individuals, including the right to due process, the presumption of innocence, and protection from torture and ill-treatment (Brants & Franken, 2009).

Some investigation agencies, such as the Commission of Inquiry on Enforced Disappearances (COIED), are specifically tasked with investigating human rights violations. By holding perpetrators accountable for these crimes, these agencies contribute to seeking justice for victims and deterring future violations.

4.9.4 Strengthening Rule of Law

Investigation agencies contribute to strengthen the rule of law by enforcing laws and regulations impartially and without bias. By investigating crimes and prosecuting offenders, these agencies demonstrate that everyone, regardless of their status or position, is subject to the law.

Investigation agencies also play a role in promoting legal frameworks that uphold justice and accountability. Through their actions and advocacy, these agencies contribute to the development

and implementation of laws and policies that protect the rights of individuals and promote accountability (Mahmod, 2013).

4.9.5 Building Public Trust

Transparent and accountable investigation processes help build public trust in government institutions. By demonstrating integrity, professionalism, and impartiality in their work, investigation agencies inspire confidence in their ability to deliver justice and uphold the rule of law.

Building public trust requires engagement with the community and stakeholders. Investigation agencies can enhance transparency and accountability by soliciting feedback, providing updates on investigations, and addressing concerns raised by the public (Zafarullah & Siddiquee, 2021).

4.9.6 Preventing Impunity

Investigation agencies in Pakistan play a pivotal role in preventing impunity by ensuring that individuals responsible for committing crimes are held accountable. This commitment to accountability sends a clear message that crime will not be tolerated, deterring future criminal behavior and fostering a culture of compliance with the law. By holding perpetrators accountable, Pakistan's investigation agencies contribute to the prevention of crimes and the promotion of justice within the country (Simon & Witchel, 2021).

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Improving the role of investigation agencies in maintaining peace and order in Pakistan requires a multifaceted approach that addresses various challenges and enhances the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts. Here are several recommendations:

5.1 Enhance Resources and Capacity-Building: Allocate sufficient resources, including funding, manpower, and technological infrastructure, to investigation agencies. Invest in training programs to enhance the skills and capabilities of law enforcement personnel, particularly in areas such as forensic investigation, intelligence analysis, and cyber-crime detection. Strengthening the capacity of investigation agencies will enable them to respond more effectively to emerging security threats and carry out their duties more efficiently.

5.2 Reduce Political Interference: Ensure the independence and autonomy of investigation agencies by insulating them from political interference. Implement measures to safeguard the

integrity of law enforcement operations and prevent undue influence from political actors. Uphold the rule of law and ensure that investigation agencies operate impartially and transparently, without fear or favor.

5.3 Improve Coordination and Collaboration: Foster closer coordination and collaboration among investigation agencies, law enforcement bodies, and other relevant stakeholders. Establish mechanisms for sharing intelligence, coordinating operations, and conducting joint initiatives to address complex security challenges. Enhancing inter-agency cooperation will facilitate more effective responses to crime and terrorism, improve information sharing, and optimize resource utilization.

5.4 Combat Corruption and Ensure Accountability: Implement robust anti-corruption measures within investigation agencies to combat corruption and uphold integrity. Strengthen internal oversight mechanisms, establish whistleblower protection programs, and promote transparency in law enforcement operations. Hold accountable those found guilty of corruption or misconduct, regardless of rank or position, to restore public trust in investigation agencies and the criminal justice system.

5.5 Utilize Technology and Innovation: Embrace technological advancements and innovation to enhance the capabilities of investigation agencies. Invest in state-of-the-art forensic tools, surveillance equipment, and data analytics technologies to improve crime detection, evidence collection, and intelligence analysis. Leverage digital platforms and social media monitoring to identify and disrupt criminal activities, particularly in cyberspace.

5.6 Empower Community Engagement: Foster closer ties between investigation agencies and the communities they serve through community policing initiatives, neighborhood watch programs, and public outreach campaigns. Encourage citizen participation in crime prevention efforts, provide avenues for reporting suspicious activities, and solicit community feedback to inform law enforcement priorities and strategies.

5.7 Promote Human Rights and Rule of Law: Uphold human rights principles and adhere to the rule of law in all law enforcement activities. Ensure that investigation agencies respect the rights of suspects, detainees, and victims, and conduct investigations in accordance with due process and legal safeguards. Provide training on human rights standards and accountability

mechanisms to law enforcement personnel to prevent abuses and ensure accountability for violations.

5.8 Engage in Research and Evaluation: Conduct research and evaluation to assess the effectiveness of investigation agencies' strategies and initiatives in maintaining peace and order. Monitor key performance indicators, analyse crime trends, and solicit feedback from stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and refine law enforcement approaches. Utilize evidence-based practices and lessons learned to inform policy decisions and resource allocation. By implementing these recommendations, Pakistan can strengthen the role of investigation agencies in maintaining peace and order, enhance public safety, and build a more secure and resilient society. These efforts require sustained commitment, collaboration, and investment in building the capacity and integrity of law enforcement institutions to effectively address the evolving security challenges facing the country.

6. CONCLUSION

The promotion of justice and accountability through investigation agencies in Pakistan is vital for upholding the rule of law, ensuring transparency, and fostering public trust in government institutions. Throughout this paper, we have explored the significant role that investigation agencies play in combating corruption, ensuring fair trials, protecting human rights, strengthening the rule of law, building public trust, and preventing impunity.

Firstly, investigation agencies such as the NAB are at the forefront of combating corruption in Pakistan. By investigating cases of corruption, bribery, and embezzlement, these agencies hold public officials and individuals accountable for misusing public resources and abusing their positions of power. The NAB, in particular, has been instrumental in investigating high-profile corruption cases and recovering looted assets, demonstrating its commitment to promoting accountability and transparency.

Secondly, investigation agencies contribute to ensuring fair trials by gathering evidence and building cases against individuals accused of committing crimes. Through adherence to due process and presentation of evidence in court, these agencies uphold the principles of justice and equity. By conducting impartial and thorough investigations, they contribute to the delivery of justice and the protection of individuals' rights.

Moreover, investigation agencies are tasked with protecting human rights while conducting investigations and apprehending suspects. By respecting the rights of individuals, including the right to due process and the presumption of innocence, these agencies promote justice and accountability in their actions. Furthermore, some investigation agencies are specifically mandated to investigate human rights violations, such as extrajudicial killings, enforced disappearances, and torture. By holding perpetrators accountable for these crimes, these agencies contribute to seeking justice for victims and deterring future violations.

Additionally, investigation agencies play a crucial role in strengthening the rule of law by enforcing laws and regulations impartially and without bias. By investigating crimes and prosecuting offenders, these agencies demonstrate that everyone, regardless of their status or position, is subject to the law. This contributes to a more just, transparent, and accountable society where the rule of law prevails.

Building public trust in government institutions is another essential aspect of the promotion of justice and accountability. Transparent and accountable investigation processes help build public trust by demonstrating integrity, professionalism, and impartiality in their work. When investigation agencies operate with transparency and accountability, they inspire confidence in their ability to deliver justice and uphold the rule of law, thus fostering trust between citizens and the government.

Furthermore, investigation agencies prevent impunity by holding accountable those responsible for committing crimes. By ensuring that perpetrators face consequences for their actions, these agencies deter future criminal behavior and contribute to a more just and equitable society. The prosecution of criminals sends a clear message that impunity will not be tolerated, thereby promoting accountability and deterring potential wrongdoers.

In conclusion, the promotion of justice and accountability through investigation agencies in Pakistan is essential for the country's socio-economic development, stability, and progress. By combating corruption, ensuring fair trials, protecting human rights, strengthening the rule of law, building public trust, and preventing impunity, these agencies play a crucial role in upholding democratic values and principles. However, to effectively promote justice and accountability, investigation agencies must operate with integrity, professionalism, and a commitment to upholding the principles of justice and fairness. Additionally, they must collaborate with other

stakeholders, including the judiciary, civil society organizations, and international partners, to address systemic challenges and promote a culture of accountability and transparency in Pakistan. Ultimately, by promoting justice and accountability, investigation agencies contribute to building a more just, equitable and prosperous society for all citizens.

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